

IN SCHOOL AT SUMMER: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONAL LEARNING CAMP

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In School at Summer: A Multiple Case Study on the Implementation of National Learning Camp

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Abstract

This multiple-case study aimed to explore and understand the experiences of school principal, mathematics teacher, parent, and student who were involved in the implementation of the national learning camp. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating four (4) participants who were involved in the implementation of the national learning camp were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interviews. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: struggling with maintaining student engagement and attendance; sacrificing rest and vacation over academic responsibilities; and experiencing learning through innovative and enjoyable methods. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deem the following coping strategies essential: maintaining a positive outlook and behavior; utilizing technology-based interventions to enhance learning; giving positive reinforcement and motivation; and considering the learning styles of students. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: strengthening partnerships among stakeholders to enhance student support; empowering academic excellence and student engagement; integrating engaging activities in teaching and learning process; and integrating interactive materials to improve classroom instruction. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, school principals, mathematics teachers, parents, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *National Learning Camp, mathematics, qualitative, multiple-case, Philippines*

Introduction

The problems in learning mathematics among students are evident especially in conceptual understanding, procedural knowledge, and problem-solving skills. To help close learning gaps, the Department of Education, as articulated in MATATAG: Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa agenda, has committed to a learning recovery program to address learning losses arising from the COVID-19 pandemic. The implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) is a strategic initiative to improve skills in reading, mathematics, science, and technology. Furthermore, DepEd also cited results from National Achievement Tests and international large-scale assessments highlighting the need for additional teaching support to enhance learners' academic performance (Dela Peña, 2023). However, the Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) pointed out that DepEd's implementation of the NLC would deprive teachers' and students' right to ample rest and time to recuperate (Hernando-Malipot, 2023).

In South Africa, particularly in Namibia, a lack of mathematical problem-solving skills has been observed among the Junior Secondary (Grade 8-9) learners which contribute to poor performance in mathematics (DNEA, 2021). Moreover, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Basic Education in South Africa reported that school closures in 2020 resulted in an average loss of 54% of in-person learning time for that year. This means that learners fell behind during the pandemic because they received far less instruction than in a normal year. To close the learning gaps, the Tswelopele Campaign (Remote Learning Campaign) was developed to provide learners with instructional materials to catch up on learning losses through television, mobile chat platforms and YouTube channels (DBE, 2022). However, the learning recovery program's guidelines mainly focused on planning for learning recovery and delegated decision-making to teachers without allocating additional time or resources for significant changes beyond 'business-as-usual' teaching (Hoadley, 2023).

Furthermore, based on the recent Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2022 test results, the Department of Education's National Report of the Philippines (2023) indicates that only 16% of Filipino students reached at least the minimum proficiency level (Level 2) in mathematics literacy (Chi, 2023). These findings show that mathematics education in the country needs to be improved. In response to this, and due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Education implemented the national learning camp. However, the senate committee on basic education chairperson senator Sherwin Gatchalian raised the issue of the DepEd's learning camp project not capturing those students who need it the most. Also, when the EDCOM II Executive Director visited in Taguig National High School, it was found out that the students with that needed remediation – those who were most needed to be in the camps – were not there (De Villa, 2024).

Thus, there is urgency in conducting this study because the researcher could not find any previous studies on how school principal, mathematics teacher, parent, and student' experiences in the implementation of the national learning camp contribute as a precursor in students having difficulty in learning mathematics. Considering this, these students need urgent assistance in developing competence in other essential mathematical processes and concepts. Essentially, this study has social significance since it could be used as a scientific framework for improving learning performance for students and strengthening teacher capacity, as fulfilled by the mathematics teachers at the actual institution where the study was carried out.

The research underscores a significant gap in understanding an issue in terms of difficulty in learning mathematics such as the study of Gafoor and Kurukkan (2015) entitled "Learner and Teacher perception on Difficulties in Learning and Teaching Mathematics: Some

Implications”, the empirical study of Moser Opitz, et. al (2016), entitled “Remediation for Students with Mathematics Difficulties: An Intervention Study in Middle Schools”, and, the study by Scherer et.al (2017), entitled “Assistance of Students with Mathematical Learning Difficulties—how can research support practice?—A summary”. Due to the lack of previous studies, this study is conceived to explore the experiences of school principal, mathematics teacher, parent, and student in the implementation of the national learning camp in Kapalong District, Division of Davao del Norte.

Research Questions

This study aimed to find out and understand the experiences of school principal, mathematics teacher, parents, and student in the implementation of the national learning camp. Thus, important questions that were tackled were as follows:

1. What are the challenges of the school principal, mathematics teacher, parent, and student in the implementation of the national learning camp?
2. How do they cope with the challenges?
3. What improvement can you suggest to improve the implementation of the national learning camp?

Literature Review

Challenges in Learning Mathematics

Mathematics learning difficulties can be attributed to shortcomings in one or more skill areas. Initially, students may not fully grasp basic number facts, struggle with calculations, face challenges in transferring knowledge and making connections, and may not fully understand the language of mathematics. They may also encounter difficulties in comprehending visual and spatial aspects and perceptual issues. Additionally, prior research has supported the notion that difficulties in learning mathematics may stem from an individual's lower skill level, possibly due to missed opportunities to learn mathematics and perhaps a lack of practice and preparation in mathematics (Rameriz et al., 2018).

Further, a study revealed that the difficulties experienced by students in learning mathematics are the difficulty in understanding explanations and the intentions of the questions, the difficulty in understanding material and symbols in mathematics, and the difficulty in carrying out calculations. The methods used by the teacher to overcome this are motivating students, using varied methods, and tutoring students. However, the process of overcoming these problems is not explained in detail. The results of this study are still straightforward, so there is a need for in-depth studies related to students' learning difficulties in mathematics (Febriyanti et al., 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

The method used in this study was a qualitative research design that employed multiple case study as a strategy of inquiry. Qualitative multiple case studies offer a descriptive analysis to understand the differences and similarities between cases (Baxter & Jack, 2008). Through this, the study was able to collect crucial data that aided in understanding the experiences of the school principal, mathematics teacher, parent, and student involved in the implementation of the national learning camp. By conducting interviews, describing the experiences, difficulties, and insights of the participants of the study, and then analyzing the data, a qualitative design is used to explore and comprehend the unique cases, statements, and insights of the participants.

Participants

The main participants of this study were the school principal, mathematics teacher, parent, and student involved in the implementation of the national learning camp. Only four (4) participants within the Division of Davao del Norte engaged in this inquiry. Also, one (1) informant was interviewed for each participant to support their distinct responses to the given research questions. This number was chosen in accordance with Creswell's recommendation that there should be between three (3) and five (5) participants in a case study (Creswell, 2013). By incorporating this group of participants in a qualitative research study, data saturation was attained in the data gathering procedure.

Moreover, purposive sampling was employed to identify the participants which refers to a class of non-probability sampling techniques. Thus, participants were selected based on the following inclusion criteria: they were all involved in the implementation of the national learning camp and were within the Kapalong District, Division of Davao del Norte. Further, to specifically select participants, those aged fifteen to forty-six (15–46) are chosen.

Procedure

The researcher followed a structured protocol covering all phases of data collection. First, interview guide questions were created and validated by a panel, after which the researcher obtained an endorsement letter and the adviser's approval. With permission from the Division Superintendent of DepEd-Davao del Norte, the researcher proceeded to request authorization to conduct face-to-face interviews with the school principal, mathematics teacher, parent, and student involved in the national learning camp in Kapalong District, Division of Davao del Norte.

After receiving approval, the researcher sent letters to selected participants requesting consent to join the study and provided consent forms for those willing. Before starting, the researcher held an orientation to explain the study's purpose, methodology, participant rights, and obtained permission to record the interviews. Following the interviews, the researcher transcribed the data, verified it with participants, and proceeded to analyze the findings to draw conclusions and recommendations.

Data Analysis

The collected data from the in-depth interviews were transcribed, translated, and analyzed following Creswell's proposed process for data analysis (Creswell, 2009). The researcher followed the steps recommended by Creswell. The translated responses of the participants were coded to create a thematic analysis of the data for this case study. Thematic analysis, also known as coding, involves categorizing responses and identifying recurring themes in the text to develop a structured representation of thematic ideas. These significant themes provide valuable insights into the data that can be further analyzed and measured. Through the systematic process of thematic analysis, the researcher organized the dataset into themes or patterns. This enabled the researcher to identify and develop themes based on the obtained data. During the data analysis, the researcher relied on the transcripts and translations of the informants' responses. Using the coding process, the researcher grouped and organized the repeated responses to generate a comprehensive theme analysis. The concepts were sorted and evaluated based on their relationships, similarities, and contrasts, with the assistance of a data analyst.

Ethical Considerations

When collecting data from individuals, scientists and researchers always adhered to a set of ethical principles that guided research designs and procedures. Ethical guidelines must be followed during research to uphold academic or scientific integrity, enhance research validity, and protect the rights of research participants (Bhandari, 2022). Further, this research work adhered to the Belmont Report of 1979, as cited by Anabo (2019), which outlines the following principles: respect for persons, beneficence, and justice while working with the individuals who participated in this research. Thus, the study maintained the safety and secrecy, as well as provided them with complete security, so that they did not lose trust throughout the study.

Results and Discussion

The qualitative research questions were answered using data collected through in-depth interviews conducted independently for each case. In-depth interviews were done by the researcher in order to address the phenomena in depth and give the informants a platform to describe their experiences in detail and as accurately as possible. The information gleaned from the interview is only accessible to the researcher and the participant (Mills et al., 2010). Following that, the themes were generated using both case and cross-case analysis, which were meticulously adhered to for the benefit of the research.

Case 1 – School Principal (IDI-01)

This case consisted of a school principal who was involved in the implementation of the national learning camp and was within the Kapalong District, Division of Davao del Norte. Her leadership style is characterized by a strong dedication to motivating both teachers and students. Moreover, the school principal plays a crucial role in ensuring the success of the national learning camp by leading its implementation and motivating both teachers and students to actively participate.

Case 2 – Mathematics Teacher (IDI-02)

This case consisted of a mathematics teacher who was involved in the implementation of the national learning camp and was within the Kapalong District, Division of Davao del Norte. She has made a significant contribution to the enjoyable and effective implementation of the national learning camp by serving as a mentor and elder on top to being a teacher.

Case 3 – Student (IDI-03)

This case consisted of a student who was involved in the implementation of the national learning camp and was within the Kapalong District, Division of Davao del Norte. She willingly takes on the role of group leader, planning and explaining activities for her peers, particularly when they are hesitant to speak with teachers. Further, the student saw her role in the national learning camp as actively participating by answering questions from the teachers and taking the initiative to respond during discussions.

Case 4 – Parent (IDI-04)

This case consisted of a parent of a student who was involved in the implementation of the national learning camp and was within the Kapalong District, Division of Davao del Norte. The parent's role during the national learning camp was to provide strong support and encouragement, motivating her child to actively participate despite it being the summer break.

Cross-Case Analysis on Experiences of School Principal, Mathematics Teacher, Parent, and Student in the Implementation of the National Learning Camp

There were three major themes emerged in this study: struggling with maintaining student engagement and attendance; sacrificing rest and vacation over academic responsibilities; and experiencing learning through innovative and enjoyable methods. These themes are

shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Cross-Case Analysis on Experiences of School Principal, Mathematics Teacher, Parent, and Student in the Implementation of the National Learning Camp*

Emerging Themes	Thematic Statements
Struggling with Maintaining Student Engagement and Attendance	<p>“Since there are some students who failed or who denied that they had that difficulty. On the denial, they tend to be absent on the class, so on that part we do have that hardships since we have to get again the students make sunda sa balay. Pero katong mga bright perting abtika moadto ug skwelahan, sila pa hinoon to abtik.” (IDI-01)</p> <p>(Some students failed or denied having that difficulty. They tend to be absent in class. So, we do have hardships since we have to fetch the students from their homes again. However, the bright ones are very active in going to school; they are the ones who are very diligent.)</p> <p>“Those kanang naglisod jud sa math, tas nag join sila, ang hardships jud namo is we experienced kanang daghan ug absents. Oo, mayra ra sila sa sugod, molahotay pa sila, pagkadugayan ma bored na sila, sige na silag absent, dili na sila ganahan mobalik kuntahay mo skwela karong buntag pagka hapon mouli napud sila. Naa poy uban nga mo absent buntag tas mo skwelag hapon. Ingon ana jud sila.” (IDI-02)</p> <p>(For those who struggled with math and then joined, our hardship was that we experienced a lot of absences. Yes, they would attend at first, but as time went on, they would get bored, frequently absent, and not want to come back. Sometimes, they would attend school in the morning and go back home in the afternoon. Some would be absent in the morning and attend school in the afternoon. That is how they were.)</p>
Sacrificing Rest and Vacation over Academic Responsibilities	<p>“Akoang nabati ato nga time kay naami lisod nga lesson nga dili kaayo namo usahay masabtan kay sa isa ka room is daghan man sad mi ba tas lahi-lahi gani mig way nga makatuon so para sa akoa kay maglisod ko ug sabot if visual presentation lang gani ang gamiton ni ma’am. Kuan pud ya maglisod pud mig sabot sa mga unfamiliar na gani nga mga concepts sa math kanang mabag-ohan mi.” (IDI-03)</p> <p>(That is also challenging for us because it is nice to have group activities, and if some of our group members are absent and they have a part where they are supposed to present, then it becomes difficult for us when there are absences because our presentation will not be complete during activities.)</p> <p>“It was very surprising actually, with the announcement because it should be done right away even though naulahi ug announced, I was just surprised that there are still some teachers who were willing to volunteer to be part of the camp. And frustrating on the other hand since most of the teachers are expecting to abroad or have their vacation.” (IDI-01)</p> <p>(I was very surprised by the announcement because it should have been done right away even though it was announced late, I was just surprised that there were still some teachers who were willing to volunteer to be part of the camp. And frustrating, on the other hand since most of the teachers are expecting to go abroad or have their vacation.)</p>
Experiencing Learning through Innovative and Enjoyable Methods	<p>“Pero naguol sad baya ko ato kay kanang summer naman unta to ba makapahulay pa akong anak unta sa mga buluhaton sa skwelahan kay usahay ba busy na kaayo na siya pag uli kay gabuhat sa mga assignment ana. Oo, naguol ko nga nalipay kay basin ma stress siya kung mag sigeg study ba ana.” (IDI-04)</p> <p>(But I was also worried because it was supposed to be summer, and I hoped my child would have some rest from schoolwork since sometimes they are already busy with assignments. Yes, I was happy, but I was worried that it might stress them out if they had to study continuously.)</p> <p>“Since the mode of learning is different from the normal delivery, it is more fun actually compared to the normal days. So, exciting kaayo sila moadto sa school much more that they were given free snacks, dula, then naga innovate si mathematics teachers on how to make mathematics funnier or dali ra masabtan. I have heard one of the mathematics teachers saying na ingon ani nalang kaya ma’am no bisan sa regular days kay murag dali ra lagi kaayo makasabot ang mga bata ug ingon ani nga pamaagi, nindot siya.” (IDI-01)</p> <p>(Since the mode of learning is different from the normal delivery, it was more fun compared to the normal days. So, they are very excited to go to school, especially since they are given free snacks and games, and every day the mathematics teachers innovate on how to make mathematics more fun and easier to understand. I have heard one of the mathematics teachers saying that this approach works even better than regular days because the children seem to understand things more easily with this method, and it is great.)</p> <p>“Para sa akoa kay enjoy siya nga camp kay daghan mi ug natun-an tas lingaw siya kay daghan ug mga activities nga kanang ganahan gani mi dulaon to siya tapos labi na sa math games na kay enjoy makatuon ug math pinaagi sa dula. Unya makaingon sad mi nga kanang dili gud boring ang pagtudlo kay dili lang man mi permi ga lecture si ma’am kanang nagadula man jud mi so mas makatuon mi kay lingaw man sad siya dulaon.” (IDI-03)</p> <p>(For me, the camp was enjoyable because we learned a lot and had fun. There were many activities that we liked to play, especially the math games, because it was enjoyable to learn math through games. We can also say that the teaching was not boring because we were not always lectured by the teacher; instead, we often played, so we learned while having fun.)</p>

The first theme of this study revealed that participants were struggling with maintaining student engagement and attendance during the national learning camp. This result was supported by the claim of Skilling et al. (2021) which explained that students who had a strong interest in mathematics but lacked proficiency in the topic were more likely to participate in the problems they were working on than students who had proficiency in the subject but lacked enthusiasm. Similarly, this was supported by the study conducted by Zubrick

(2019) which explained that one of the prevalent issues facing teachers nowadays is absenteeism. According to some experts, students who miss two or more days of class are classified as chronic absentees, and they typically receive low grades. Students' low attendance at school might have a significant impact on their academic achievement.

The second theme of this study revealed that participants experienced sacrificing rest and vacation over academic responsibilities. This is the practice of putting academic obligations—like studying, homework, and research—above vacation plans, leisure activities, and taking breaks. This study results conformed to the study conducted by Zydziunaite et al. (2020) which explained that sacrificing rest over academic responsibilities are related to the excessive workloads of the teachers. In fact, teacher workloads are excessive and intensive, and the negative effects associated with an unrealistic workload are having a considerable impact on teaching quality, the quality of teachers' work life, and on students' learning achievements and experiences.

The third theme of this study revealed that participants experiencing learning through innovative and enjoyable methods. The result of the study adapted the work of Bawuro (2018) who states that teachers differ in their teaching strategies. As a result, teachers employ various teaching strategies based on the courses they are teaching, the kinds of students they are teaching, the size of the class, and the resources the classroom has to provide. This covers think-pair-share, gamification, learning stations, flipped classrooms, student-centered learning, learning by doing, and role-playing. Furthermore, the findings of this study observed to the claim of Variacion et al. (2021) which explained that if the learning tasks obtained by students are in accordance with their abilities and understanding and are able to encourage students to do them in the way they like, then students can learn better.

Cross-Case Analysis on Coping Mechanisms of School Principal, Mathematics Teacher, Parent, and Student in the Implementation of the National Learning Camp

There were four major themes emerged in this study: maintaining a positive outlook and behavior; utilizing technology-based interventions to enhance learning; giving positive reinforcement and motivation; and considering the learning styles of students. These themes are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. *Cross-Case Analysis on Coping Mechanisms of School Principal, Mathematics Teacher, Parent, and Student in the Implementation of the National Learning Camp*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Thematic Statements</i>
Maintaining a Positive Outlook and Behavior	<p>“Of course, as a teacher, you have to maintain your composure, you have to be a good, what pretender that you still have that feeling nga dili ka mo surrender for them. Kaya pa nimo despite of everything.” (IDI-01) (Of course, as a teacher, you have to maintain your composure; you have to be adept at pretending that you still have that feeling that you will not surrender to them. You can still manage despite everything.)</p> <p>“Stay calm in every situation encountered and think positive as always. By listening to their weary struggle, paminawon jud nimo asa naglisod, then answer their questions as well kung naay mga pangutana, queries, tapos in a calm and positive manner lang jud perminte. Bahalag kanang gibalik balik na nila ang pangutana, bahalag kanang gibalik ra gani ilang pangutana unya obvious na gani kaayo, motubag lang pud. Stay calm in every situation encountered and think positive as always.” (IDI-02) (Stay calm in every situation encountered and think positively as always. By listening to their weary struggle, you will truly understand where they are having difficulties, then answer their questions as well if there are any queries. Respond calmly and positively, even if they keep asking the same questions repeatedly, or even if the question seems obvious, just answer calmly. Stay calm in every situation encountered and think positively as always.)</p> <p>“Sabton lang jud nako akong kaugalingon nga maglisod gani pud ta usahay then dili lang pud mag breakdown gani kaayo ya kay sa sige natog tuon ana kay makasabot raman sad ta kadugayan ya. Pag naami kalisod kay stay positive lang jud always pud ya kay makasabot raman pud mi if mag patabang nami sa teacher ana. Dili lang jud ipalabi atong mga kalagot, negative emotions ana para hapsay ang tanan.” (IDI-03) (I just tell myself that sometimes we struggle, but we should not break down because as we keep studying, we eventually understand. When things get tough, I just stay positive because we will eventually understand, especially if we ask the teacher for help. We should not let our frustrations and negative emotions take over to keep everything in order.)</p> <p>“Sabton lang jud kanunay akong anak ug kanang ang kaugalingon sad kay di man sa tanang butang nga makabalo ta ba naa man juy butang nga wala ta kabalo so mao to magsinabtanay lang mi aron di malagot o masuko kay looy man pud na akong anak kung akoa panang kasab an ana.” (IDI-04) (My child and I always respond to each other and acknowledge that it is okay not to know everything because there are always things we do not know. So, we understand each other to avoid getting frustrated or upset because I will not want my child to feel bad if I react negatively.)</p>
Utilizing Technology-based Interventions to Enhance Learning	<p>“Technology resources so yes, they were given, they are actually having that television then all of the resources were provided actually by the Department of Education. All they have to do is to present it in the class, ana lang that's good. So, nakatabang jud tog ma enhance ilahang knowledge on mathematics.” (IDI-01) (Technology resources were provided; yes, they were given a television, and all the resources were provided by the Department of Education. All they have to do is present it in class, that is all. So, it really helped to enhance their knowledge of mathematics.)</p> <p>“Mostly kay TV lang jud among ginagamit ato nga time. And also, pwede pud cellphones nila kay usahay naa</p>

Giving Positive Reinforcement and Motivation	<p>man mi i-apply nga kanang sa website gani, say for example. Oo, educational apps like quizizz, ouh nagagamit jud mi pero dili jud siya ingon nga permininti, kasagaran TV lang gyud. PowerPoint presentation ana lang unya video about the lesson.” (IDI-02)</p> <p>(Mostly, we only use the television during that time. And, their cellphones can be used because sometimes we have applications like websites, for example, yes, educational apps like Quizizz, oh, we use them but not regularly, mostly just the television. It is usually just PowerPoint presentations and videos about the lesson.)</p> <p>“Gagamit ko ug mga educational apps sa online like sa mathway tapos ga download sad kog mga offline nga application kanang mga scientific calculator para magamit nako if naakoy isolve. Yes, gagamit among teacher ug kanang TV para mag present ug kanang lesson nga iyang iklase tas through ana is makasabot mi. Tas kasagaran sad namo mga activity ya kay gagamit ug TV gani kanang naay mga games nga need ug ppt ana.” (IDI-03)</p> <p>(Mostly, we only use the television during that time. And, their cellphones can be used because sometimes we have applications like websites; for example, yes, educational apps like Quizizz; oh, we use them but not regularly, mostly just the television. It is usually just PowerPoint presentations and videos about the lesson.)</p> <p>“Kanang cellphone, TV, ug katong akong ginaingon sir nga magtan aw ug lecture videos sa youtube gani unya i-connect namo sa TV, aron makatuon jud akong anak sir kanang murag naa gihapoy nagtudlo maestra pinaagi sa youtube. Oo sir, kanang gintan aw man sad nako ba if makatabang bani nga video.” (IDI-04)</p> <p>(We use cellphones, television, and, as I mentioned earlier, watch lecture videos on YouTube, then connect it to the television so that my child can truly learn as if a teacher is guiding us through the YouTube videos. Yes, I also check if those videos are helpful.)</p> <p>“The reinforcements I have done is give verbal praises, positive feedback lang jud perminte bahalag mali gud ang ilahang tubag. I-ano lang jud nimo, praise lang jud nimo sila para ma motivate unya ganahan pud sila mo answer. Yeah, gahatag sad mig snacks pud.” (IDI-02)</p> <p>(The reinforcements I have done include giving verbal praise and providing positive feedback consistently, even if their answers are wrong. You just praise them to motivate them and encourage them to participate. Yeah, we also give snacks.)</p> <p>“Gina praise mi ni ma’am through ano istorya ganing thank you, good job, very good, ana. Mao to nga ma motivate mi kay gina encourage sad mi ni ma’am ya nga magtuon ana so ma boost among motivation. Oo, naami snacks ug na motivate sad mi ato nga maningkamot pajud ug tuon tungod sa snacks.” (IDI-03)</p> <p>(Ma’am praises us by saying things like 'thank you,' 'good job', 'very good,' and like that. That is why we are motivated because ma'am encourages us to study, so our motivation is boosted. Yes, the snacks are great, and they also motivate us to study harder because of the snacks.)</p> <p>“Rewards kay akoa siyang ginatagaan ug kwarta nga kanang pag naa na siyay tama ana tas usahay moingon mana siya ba nga i perfect niya ang quiz or assignment tagaan namo siyag kwarta. Mao to ipakita na dayon na niya iyang papel unya tagaan namo siyag kwarta kay mao may kalipayan rasad niya. Tag 20 ana or usahay singkwenta pero dili pud taga adlaw.” (IDI-04)</p> <p>(I give her rewards, like giving her money when she gets it right, and sometimes she says she will perfect the quiz or assignment, so we give her money. That is why she quickly shows us her paper so we can give her money because that is her joy. It is usually around 20 pesos or sometimes fifty, but not daily.)</p>
Considering the Learning Styles of Students	<p>“The factor that I consider the most is their learning styles and of course their family background no.” (IDI-02)</p> <p>(The factor that I consider the most is their learning styles and, of course, their family background.)</p> <p>“Isa sa mga akong mga gina consider aron makatuon ko kay ang akong learning style ug study habits nako kay aron makapangita ko ug way nga kanang makatuon ko sa lesson.” (IDI-03)</p> <p>(One of the things I consider learning is my learning style and study habits so that I can find a way to understand the lesson.)</p>

The first theme highlighted that participants were maintaining a positive outlook and behavior. This means that thinking about what is good in a situation; feeling confident and sure that something good will happen. The study's findings were connected to a study of Frenzel et al. (2021), which claims that teachers feel and show a wide range of emotions with varying quality and intensities when they are teaching and interacting with students. Teachers might feel proud of students when they achieve and satisfied when the class goes well. Further, this result was related to the study of Mercer and Dörnyei (2020) states that teachers should be approachable, believe in all their students, be empathetic, be responsive to students' individuality, support students' autonomy, and be passionate about their profession.

The second theme highlighted that participants were utilizing technology-based interventions to enhance learning. The result was supported in the work of Güney (2023), which states that the rapid development of technology has transformed the way in which K-12 education is delivered, producing new and innovative opportunities for teachers and students to engage with the material and expand their knowledge and understanding in the 21st century. Thus, the integration of smartboards, computers, tablets, and laptops into K-12 education has had a significant impact on the way students learn and teachers teach. Also, similar findings were made by Ariyanto et al. (2018), who also noted that the use of calculators by students shows that they are actively involved in the mathematical process and enhances their understanding of concepts, computing skills, and ability to display accurate answers.

The third theme highlighted that participants were giving positive reinforcement and motivation. The result was supported by the study of Arista et al. (2018), which states that giving students both verbal and nonverbal reinforcement will positively affect the learning

process and make students more active and enthusiastic. In addition, according to McPartlan et al. (2021), teachers can support students' targeted behaviors and abilities and boost their motivation and self-esteem by giving them precise and meaningful positive feedback.

The fourth theme highlighted that participants were considering the learning styles of students. The result of the study adapted the work Lincă and Matei (2024), which revealed that students' success in the learning process and achieving high academic results can also be influenced by their predominant learning style or the combination of two of the learning styles. Some students may have a predominantly visual learning style and learn through diagrams, pictures, graphs, while others may have an auditory style and learn through lectures. Similarly, according to Muttaqin et al. (2019), which states that a teacher must be knowledgeable about learning styles in order to choose a teaching approach that works with each student's unique learning preferences. Based on the research findings, understanding mathematical concepts can be enhanced by adopting David Kolb's learning style. To enhance students' proficiency in solving mathematical issues, research on the Kolb Model learning style is anticipated to be able to identify students' learning preferences.

Cross-Case Analysis on Insights of School Principal, Mathematics Teacher, Parent, and Student in the Implementation of the National Learning Camp

There were four major themes emerged in this study: strengthening partnerships among stakeholders to enhance student support; empowering academic excellence and student engagement; integrating engaging activities in teaching and learning process; and integrating interactive materials to improve classroom instruction. These themes are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. *Cross-Case Analysis on Insights of School Principal, Mathematics Teacher, Parent, and Student in the Implementation of the National Learning Camp*

Emerging Themes	Thematic Statements
Strengthening Partnerships among Stakeholders to Enhance Student Support	<p>“This has a big contribution sa partnership between parents and the school. Una, matabangan ang mga bata they will not get tutor anymore in mathematics because we do have these public-school teachers, free jud na ang learning camp. Ikaduha, actually there ahh free snacks prepared by other stakeholders, it has of course contributed to strengthening the partnership not just parents but other stakeholders. Ikatulo, parents were happy I guess that their children are in school even if it is summer time kaysa mag stay sa balay, maghapon sa gadget.” (IDI-01)</p> <p>(This has a significant contribution to the partnership between parents and the school. First, it helps the children as they will no longer need tutors in mathematics because we have these public-school teachers; the learning camp is free. Second, there are free snacks prepared by other stakeholders, which has of course contributed to strengthening the partnership not only with parents but also with other stakeholders. Third, parents were happy, I guess, that their children are in school even if it is summer time, rather than staying at home all day with gadgets.)</p> <p>“Big contribution kaayo ang national learning camp sa partnership sa stakeholders ug sa teachers it is because ganahan kaayo ang parents nga naa diri ilang mga anak kaysa daw naa sa balay nagsige ug cellphone magsige laag. So nagtrabaho sila ilahang anak kay naa ra diri, safe pagyud daw, nagtuon pajud. Ang uban pud parents kay nag donate, ug additional sa snacks, then uban pud nga naga donate sa amoa kay most commonly teachers gyud to, teachers' initiative lang gyud to. Dili lang pud sa amoa nga camp masters, tanan jud teachers ang nanghatag, mao to daghan kaayo mig ginapa snacks every day. (IDI-02)</p> <p>(The national learning camp has made a significant contribution to strengthening the partnership among stakeholders and teachers because parents appreciate that their children are here rather than at home, where they might be glued to their phones or wandering around. They feel that their children are safe and are studying here. Some parents also donate additional snacks, and others contribute to us, mostly teachers. It is not just us, the camp masters, but all the teachers who give; that is why we have a lot of snacks every day.)</p> <p>“When it comes to my parents ya kay supportive man jud sila sa akong pag-apil no kay kanang dakog tabang ang NLC ya kay parehas sakong mama nga nagatrabaho gani tas wala kaayo mabilin sa balay so mao to nakaingon siya nga mas nindot nga niapil ko kay naa rako sa school nagpadayon ug tuon kaysa sa magsige daw kog atubang ug cellphone sa balay sigeg tiktok ana. Mas maayo daw na nga naa ko diri sa skwelahan.” (IDI-03)</p>
Empowering Academic Excellence and Student Engagement	<p>“Mas napalig-on pajud ang relationship sa parents ug sa school kay ang tanan man nga parents sa mga bata nga nag-apil kay nag contribute ug gamayng tabang o dungag financial nga gastohon sa skwelahan ilabina sa mga pamaliton nga snacks sa mga bata kay kami mga parents ato naghatag ug nag contribute jud ug kanang pang snacks sa among mga bata.” (IDI-04)</p> <p>(The relationship between parents and the school is further strengthened because all the parents of the children who participated contributed financially, especially for school expenses like snacks for the children. We, parents, provided and contributed snacks for our children.)</p> <p>“Of course, for those who are already intelligent in mathematics they became more interested, they became more intelligent, and more prepared for the opening of the school year, ana sila ka confident. Nindot lang jud kaayo ang learning so far nga dili dapat siya palampason sa mga kabatan-onan. Ako pa estudyante karon, bisan pag bright ko, mas moapil pako kaysa sa mag tambay sa balay.” (IDI-01)</p> <p>(Of course, those who are already skilled in mathematics, become more interested, they become more proficient, and they become more prepared for the opening of the school year, they become confident. The</p>

learning process is good so far; it should not be underestimated by the youth. Even as a student now, even if I am bright, I would still rather participate than just stay at home.)

“It contributes a lot because most campers really enjoy their 15 days camping or learning inside the school although it is summer time makatabang jud siya kaysa naman naa ra sila sa gawas naa ra sa balay, mas maayo naa sila diria unya ganahan pud sila kay sa balay wala may mama nila maka prepare sailahang snacks, diria kay maminaw lang sila pagkahuman kay mag snacks na sila.” (IDI-02)

(It contributes a lot because most campers enjoy their 15 days camping or learning inside the school even though it is summertime. It helps because instead of them being outside or at home, they should be here, and they enjoy it too because at home, there is no one to prepare snacks for them, but here, they just listen and then they have snacks afterward.)

“iingon nako sailaha ang akong kaagi ug unsa ka enjoy mag apil sa learning camp kay lingaw jud siya labi na sa mga activities nga makatabang jud siya para makasabot sa kanang math nga lessons. Tapos ano pud i encourage nako ang uban students nga mag join kaysa naman magpondo ra sa balay. Mas maka learn pa sila pag mag participate sila aning learning camp in the future.” (IDI-03)

(I tell them about my experience and how enjoyable it is to participate in the learning camp because it is fun, especially with the activities that help us understand the math lessons. Then, I also encourage other students to join instead of just staying at home. They will learn more if they participate in this learning camp in the future.)

“As a parent, makita man jud nako nga kanang naay progress sa akong anak labi na sa kanang iyang natun an sa math so akong maingon sa mga uban parents sama nako no nga kanang paapilon ilahang anak aning learning camp kay dili lang man makatuon ilahang anak kundili malingaw pajud sa mga padula kay ako malingaw man sad ko magtan aw nga enjoy sila ana.” (IDI-04)

(As a parent, I can see the progress in my child, especially in her math skills, so I tell other parents like me that they should let their children join this learning camp because not only will their children learn, but they will also have fun with the games. I also enjoy watching them.)

Integrating Engaging Activities in Teaching and Learning Process

“Actually, the plan itself, the material itself are really very good na. Ang pag integrate nalang, ang pag innovate nalang especially if you have this ahn dili haum ang imong lessons na gigamit sa intelligence sa mga bata.” (IDI-01)

(The plan itself, and the material itself are very good. It is just the integration and the innovation, especially if you have these lessons that challenge the intelligence of the children.)

“I think is just only the covered lesson or the module for the entire summer camp, it should be engaging, kanang naagyuy activities nga kanang malingaw jud ang mga bata, ma enjoy jud sila like dili lang gud mi purely mag discuss, then dili sila ma bored, tapos kanang ma-encourage pud ang mga bata nga mo join every summer. Kanang ma motivate jud sila nga ay moapil napud ko sa sunod. Ang malingawan jud nila kay ang dula jud, kadahapon magdula pero usahay kay i-alternate pud namo.” (IDI-02)

(I think it is important that the lessons or modules covered throughout the entire summer camp are engaging, with activities that truly entertain the children, so they can enjoy themselves and not get bored. We should not just purely discuss topics; we need to keep them engaged and motivated to join every summer. They should feel encouraged to participate again next time. They enjoy playing games, so we make sure to incorporate plenty of playtime. Sometimes we alternate, playing games in the morning and having classes in the afternoon; that is how we keep it balanced.)

“Maybe kanang for teachers kay dapat ang mga activities kay more on game-based gani ya kanang dula-dula nga related rapud sa math para mas lingaw pud siya ug mas masabtan namog dali ang lesson kung ipaagi sa dula.” (IDI-03)

“Ang akong ma suggest lang jud sa mga teachers no kay paningkamutan nila nga naa juy matun an ang mga bata ug malingaw sila sa pagtuon bisan sa gamay lang nga panahon ba kay sayang pud ilahang time nga gigahin aning learning camp kung di sila ma enjoy.” (IDI-04)

(My suggestion to the teachers is that they should strive to ensure that the children learn and have fun while studying, even if it is just for a short period. It would be a waste of their time at the learning camp if the children do not enjoy themselves.)

Integrating Interactive Materials to Improve Classroom Instruction

“Maybe sa activities kay ang gihatag man gud sa DepEd is module tapos purely kanang answeran jud siya. So, katong nag meeting mi during sa among NLC is dapat naa siyay kanang mga fun games, oo fun activities nga i-incorporate kay para malingaw pud ang mga bata. Parehas raman gud ang settings. So, mao to among kuan maybe next time, unta lang naajoy ingon ana nga kanang i-provide ang DepEd nga materials.” (IDI-02)

(Maybe in the activities, what DepEd provides is modules where they simply have to answer questions. So, during our meeting for our National Learning Camp (NLC), we discussed the need for fun games and activities to be incorporated so that the children can enjoy themselves, not just have the same settings all the time. So, that is what we suggested for next time, hoping that the materials provided by DepEd will include such enjoyable activities.)

“ano pud mag gamit ug klase-klase nga technology gani kay para mas nindot ang pagtudlo sa teachers pag naami gani makita nga lahi-lahi nga technologies like kanang mga interactive powerpoint tas video ana.” (IDI-03)

(They should also use various types of technology because it enhances teaching. When teachers utilize different technologies like interactive PowerPoint presentations and videos, it improves the quality of teaching.)

The first theme revealed that participants during the learning camp contributed to strengthening partnerships among stakeholders to enhance student support. Stakeholder partnership is crucial for addressing all relevant concerns, ensuring inclusivity, and enhancing decision-making processes. The result of the study was supported by the study of Mishra (2020), which states that parent and community involvement in education has long been recognized as a crucial factor in shaping the educational experiences and outcomes of students.

The second theme revealed that participants collaboratively fostered a culture of empowering academic excellence and student engagement. Student empowerment has a positive impact on academic performance. When students are empowered, their academic performance improves. The result of the study was supported by the study of Kirk et al. (2019) which revealed that highly empowered students reported better grades, fewer behavioral incidents, increased extracurricular participation and higher educational aspirations than students who were less empowered.

The third theme revealed that participants highlighted the need in integrating engaging activities in teaching and learning process. The result of the study was supported by the study of Chen et al. (2018), which explained that game-based learning gives students the opportunity to investigate challenging topics and learning settings as well as specific learning goals. To prevent students from becoming bored, games should be made so that they may repeat cycles inside the game setting. Similarly, the findings of this study observed to the claim of Kucher (2021), which states that game-based learning has more potential to boost motivation and pique students' interest in the subject matter than it does to be a better educational strategy than other learning techniques.

The fourth theme revealed that participants highlighted the need in integrating interactive materials to improve classroom instruction. The result of the study was supported by the work of Bukoye (2019), which states that instructional materials play a very important role in the teaching-learning process the availabilities of textbook, appropriate chalkboard, Mathematics kits, teaching guide, science guide, audio-visual aids, overhead projector, among others are the important instructional materials. They allow the students to interact with words, symbols and ideas in ways that develop their abilities in reading, listening, solving, viewing, thinking, speaking, writing, using media and technology.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the school principal, mathematics teacher, parent, and student were involved in the implementation of the national learning camp have discussed the challenges and difficulties involved in helping students who are struggling to learn the subject. These results imply that it is necessary to find a way to improve students' mathematics performance despite the challenges. Teachers have a role to play in the student's progress and must be aware that math difficulties can happen at any point during a student's educational development.

Essentially, students who are falling behind in the topic of mathematics are having trouble grasping the fundamentals. For students who are having difficulty learning mathematics or who do not fully grasp the subject, learning camp classes are necessary. Importantly, if a student has a known difficulty with mathematics, they should not be ignored; instead, they should get help right away and participate in the implementation of national learning camp. After determining which of the students' difficulties can be addressed or resolved in the classroom through modifications such as changing teaching methods, procedures, and alternative or modified tasks.

Additionally, school principals and mathematics teachers need to identify and address students who are struggling with mathematics, as well as how to support them and select appropriate intervention measures. Particularly, the integration of various mathematical approaches into the curriculum, engaging and fun activities in every camp session, and understanding the relevance of authentic application of mathematics. Implementing the intervention therefore also carries with it the academic and general development of the students as well as the professional growth of the teachers, which will result in effective teaching and learning experiences.

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